

GENERAL UNDERSTANDING OF READING SKILLS AND THEIR DEVELOPMENT

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada o'qish mahorati tushunchasi, uning ta'lim jarayonidagi o'rni va ahamiyati haqida umumiy ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Shuningdek, o'quvchilarning o'qish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishga doir samarali usullar va strategiyalar tahlil qilinadi. O'qish nafaqat axborot olish, balki tanqidiy fikrlash, matnni tahlil qilish va mazmunni anglash kabi ko'plab kognitiv jarayonlar bilan chambarchas bog'liqdir. Maqolada o'qish ko'nikmasini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiluvchi innovatsion yondashuvlar va texnologik vositalar haqida ham fikr yuritiladi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается понятие навыка чтения, его роль и значение в образовательном процессе. Также анализируются эффективные методы и стратегии формирования и развития навыков чтения у учащихся. Чтение связано не только с получением информации, но и с развитием критического мышления, анализа текста и понимания содержания. В статье рассматриваются инновационные подходы и технологические средства, способствующие развитию навыков чтения.

Abstract: This article provides an overview of reading skills, their importance, and role in the educational process. It analyzes effective methods and strategies for developing and enhancing students' reading abilities. Reading is not only a tool for obtaining information but is also closely linked to critical thinking, text analysis, and comprehension. The article also discusses innovative approaches and technological tools that contribute to the improvement of reading proficiency.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qish mahorati, o'qish ko'nikmasi, ta'lim jarayoni, tanqidiy fikrlash, matn tahlili, innovatsion yondashuv, o'quv strategiyalari

Ключевые слова: навык чтения, процесс обучения, критическое мышление, анализ текста, стратегии обучения, инновационные подходы

Keywords: reading skills, reading proficiency, educational process, critical thinking, text analysis, learning strategies, innovative approaches

Introduction

Reading is one of the most fundamental language skills that plays a crucial role in the academic, professional, and personal development of individuals. It is not only a means of acquiring information but also a tool for enhancing critical thinking, expanding vocabulary, and developing analytical skills. In the modern educational context, reading proficiency is considered an essential component of literacy and lifelong learning. However, developing effective reading skills requires more than just the ability to decode words — it involves comprehension, interpretation, and reflection. This paper explores the concept of reading skills, their significance in the learning process, and practical strategies for improving reading abilities among learners. Furthermore, the article highlights innovative approaches and technologies that can support and enhance reading development in both traditional and digital learning environments.

Reading is a significant part of educational process. Reading is the receptive skill in the written mode. It can develop independently of listening and speaking skills, but often develops along with them, especially in societies with a highly-developed literary tradition. Reading can help build vocabulary that helps listening comprehension at the later stages, particularly.

Here are some of the micro-skills involved in reading. The reader has to:

- decipher the script. In an alphabetic system or a syllabary, this means establishing a relationship between sounds and symbols. In a pictograph system, it means associating the meaning of the words with written symbols;
- pick out key words, such as those identifying topics and main ideas;
- figure out the meaning of the words, including unfamiliar vocabulary, from the (written) context;
- recognise grammatical word classes: noun, adjective, etc.;
- detect sentence constituents, such as subject, verb, object, prepositions, etc. [1;1-b.]

Reading and Study Skill System

SURVEY Gather the Information Necessary to Focus and Formulate Goals

1. Read the title help your mind prepare to receive the subject at hand.
2. Read the introduction and/or summary orient yourself to how this chapter fits the author's purposes, and focus on the author's statement of most important points.
3. Notice each boldface heading and subheading - organise your mind before you begin to read build a structure for the thoughts and details to come.
4. Notice any graphics charts, maps, diagrams, etc. are there to make a point don't miss them.
5. Notice reading aids italics, bold face print, chapter. [1;2-b.]

Teaching reading strategies

Strategies and skills

Strategies are often contrasted with skills. Oxford (2011, p.12) explains that 'Skills are automatic and out of awareness, whereas strategies are intentional and deliberate.' It is this conscious use of a strategy to achieve either a communicative or learning goal that sets it apart from a skill and the fact that strategies are marked by their 'intentional' and 'deliberate' use makes them open to explicit teaching.

However, as Grabe (2009) points out, the distinction between strategies and skills may not be as clear cut as at first appears. To take an example from reading, while the recognition of words may be automatic (and therefore considered a reading skill) it is likely that at the beginning stages of reading conscious attention is paid to morphemes in order to facilitate that recognition, Grabe also argues that we may apply certain strategies so frequently and so successfully that they become reading habits of which we are no longer conscious. [2;57-b.]

Do we need to teach reading strategies?

Successful reading in both L1 and L2 requires the reader to develop a range of skills and strategies and the research literature is clear and consistent on the fact that explicit teaching of strategies can be very effective in promoting efficient reading and comprehension (Carrell, 1985; Grabe, 2009; Grabe and Stoller, 2011).

However, it is also often argued that the teaching of reading strategies is unnecessary on the basis that most learners can already read in their L1 and that therefore L1 strategies will be automatically accessed in L2. While it may be true that strategies will sometimes be transferred it is certainly not always the case because learners may have to cross the so-called 'language threshold' for it to happen (Grabe and Stoller, 2011, p. 43). That is to say that L2 readers must understand enough L2 vocabulary and grammar to be able to activate L1 reading strategies successfully. If there is too much unknown material, the reader is forced to devote almost their entire effort to working out potential meanings, rather than applying the more global, higher-level, strategy processes they would use in L1 reading. Therefore, whether L1 reading strategies are available will depend on the L2 proficiency of the learner and the level of difficulty inherent in the text. [2;57-b.]

For each student, a careful local reading skill use score was calculated based on the questionnaire items that targeted this local reading behaviour. What the scores show is that in both samples more than half of the students reported to have used careful local reading frequently with an additional 27% of the students in the category of moderate users (cf. Table 29). The percentage of students in the infrequent category decreased almost by half in the 2019 sample compared to the 2015 sample, whereas the percentage of the frequent careful local reading skills users increased. [3;153-b.] Developing students' reading skills is a critical goal that begins in the primary grades. Yet with each successive grade, students must acquire increasing skills at reading and understanding a variety of texts. The Poet and the Professor: Poems for Building Reading Skills provides valuable instructional tools and engaging materials and activities for increasing student skills in reading, writing, listening, and speaking. As you use the poems, lessons, and activities in this book, you will know that you are not only providing instruction based on solid educational research, but also giving students opportunities to learn and practice specific academic standards. [4;4-b.] If science teachers were asked how they improve their students' reading skills, the majority would most likely struggle to answer the question. Good teachers use many strategies to enhance students' reading comprehension, and it is helpful to identify which strategies they use in order to explain why the technique successfully improves their students skills. Even more important is the explicit instruction of the individual strategies, including modeling, guided practice, and independent practice. These steps ensure that students learn to independently and consistently use a wide variety of reading comprehension strategies for a broad range of reading experiences. Teaching students the strategies to improve their comprehension is nothing new to educators. Research (Duke and Pearson 2002) (Block 1999; Dole, Brown, and Trathen 1996; Durkin 1978/1979; Pressley and Afflerbach 1995, as cited by Kragler, Walker, and Martin 2005) has demonstrated that students greatly benefit from the direct instruction of reading comprehension strategies when reading a text. Simply put, strategy instruction is an effective means of assisting students in comprehension and improving understanding . [5;13-b.]

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